

“Why do I have to be perfect?”

Adverse childhood experiences, perceived parenting styles, and multidimensional perfectionism

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The present study explored the link between adverse childhood experiences, perceived parenting styles, and multidimensional perfectionism. The sample comprised 156 Romanian students aged 18 to 51 ($M^{\text{age}} = 23.6$). We investigated the associations between the primary variables and the potential gender differences. We also tested a prediction model related to the multidimensional approach to perfectionism, using adverse childhood experiences and perceived parenting styles as predictors. Our results suggested that female participants reported more frequent adverse childhood experiences, while male participants scored higher than female participants regarding perceived authoritative parenting style. Results also suggested that adverse childhood experiences and perceived parenting styles significantly predicted students' self-oriented and socially prescribed perfectionism. However, these findings highlighted that only the authoritarian parenting style might be considered when discussing the role of parenting styles in the roots of SOP and SPP, emphasising the importance of parental demandingness in the absence of parental warmth.

Keywords: adverse childhood experiences; authoritarian parenting; parenting styles; self-oriented perfectionism; socially prescribed perfectionism

Perfectionism (i.e., the tendency to expect or demand from oneself or others a high or maximum level of performance that far exceeds the requirements of the current situation; APA, 2018) is on the rise: between 1989 and 2016, self-oriented perfectionism increased by 10%, other-oriented perfectionism increased by 16%, and socially prescribed perfectionism increased by 33%. Further, data suggests that 3 in 10 adolescents express maladaptive perfectionism (Sironic & Reeve, 2015).

Perfectionism is considered a learned defence mechanism developed to address unmet psychological needs. According to Hewitt et al. (2017), these needs often reflect fundamental desires for security, belonging, significance, and interpersonal connection, stemming from five perfectionistic needs: safety, connection, control, competence, and autonomy. Perfectionists often develop a belief that achieving high standards of performance or concealing imperfections will result in positive interpersonal outcomes or prevent negative ones. Thus, perfectionistic behaviour aims for acceptance, respect, and admiration while avoiding shame, humiliation, or rejection (Hewitt et al., 2017). Adaptive perfectionism, specifically self-oriented perfectionism, has been linked to conscientiousness (Hill et al., 1997; Robinson et al., 2021). Adaptive perfectionists manage stress by mobilising internal resources to engage in problem-solving. In contrast, maladaptive perfectionists exhibit higher levels of stress, anxiety, or depression (Hewitt et al., 2017). Additionally, they tend to harbour constant doubts and engage in self-criticism as a response to failing to meet a personal standard or making a mistake (Winter, 2005).

Although it was first conceptualised as a unidimensional construct (Burns, 1980), perfectionism is now seen as multidimensional (e.g., Smith et al., 2022), and can be divided into three forms: self-oriented, socially prescribed, and other-oriented perfectionism (Hewitt & Flett, 1991). In self-oriented perfectionism, individuals are excessively preoccupied with the pursuit of perfection, often setting unrealistic expectations and applying high standards to their overall success, performance, and achievements; socially prescribed perfectionism creates individuals who perceive their social context as harsh, demanding, and overly critical, while experiencing perceived unjust and exaggerated standards; other-oriented perfectionism creates individuals who impose unrealistic standards on others, who suffer unjust and severe judgment when failing to meet these standards (Hewitt et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2016).

Self-oriented perfectionism (SOP) does not involve others in the individual's pursuit of perfection. The drive to attain perfection is intrinsic and is influenced by internal standards (Miquelon et al., 2005). Self-oriented perfectionists engage in either adaptive or maladaptive behaviours while pursuing perfection since it has been linked to psychological maladjustment and adjustment outcomes such as goal progression, positive affect, and academic achievement (Stoeber et al., 2009). Conscientiousness is characterised by motivation, organisation, discipline, and persistence (Costa & McCrae, 1992). SOP has been linked to conscientiousness (Stoeber et al., 2009, 2017) and trait emotional intelligence (Smith et al., 2015 a, b). The adaptive characteristics of SOP have been explored in many studies. Some of them suggested that although SOP might be associated with anxiety, it is also negatively correlated with procrastination Klibert et al. (2005). Additionally, SOP seems to be linked to perceived self-control and achievement motivation, implying its adaptive potential. Further, Childs and Stoeber (2010) suggested that SOP was linked to vigour, dedication, and absorption, all commitment dimensions.

In contrast, socially prescribed perfectionism (SPP) is characterised by an extrinsic need for perfection, judging by the fact that the standards are not self-imposed but are perceived as externally imposed by the social environment (Miquelon et al., 2005). SPP is characterised by psychological pressure, as conforming to external performance standards may not align with one's values, often leading to helplessness, discouragement, and demoralisation. Therefore, the individual may believe high success is required for personal and social acceptance (Hewitt et al., 2017). Research has shown that perfectionism (e.g., SPP) is considered a core vulnerability or transdiagnostic vulnerability factor in a wide range of adverse outcomes, including eating disorders (Sirois & Molnar, 2016), depression (Smith et al., 2016), and anxiety (Affrunti & Woodruff-Borden, 2014).

Smith et al. (2017) emphasised the maladaptive nature of SPP, who identified the "black and white" cognitive thinking pattern among socially prescribed perfectionists. Such individuals often process life events as complete successes or catastrophic failures, resulting in profoundly adverse effects that further successes cannot lessen. Therefore, socially prescribed perfectionists may end up engaging in suicidal ideation, trapped by psychological pain, helplessness, and anxiety. Gradually, they will

interpret every failure as evidence of their declining self-worth, leading to isolation and suicidal thoughts.

Further, unlike SOP, SPP might be positively linked to neuroticism (a maladaptive personality trait) and negatively to extraversion, openness to experience, and agreeableness (Stoeber et al., 2009). Similarly, SPP was previously found to be positively linked to several maladaptive variables, such as depression, suicide proneness, anxiety, social anxiety, exhaustion, cynicism, shame, and guilt (Childs & Stoeber, 2010; Eum & Rice, 2011; Newby et al., 2017), and negatively related to adaptive variables, such as social support (Chen et al., 2024), self-esteem, perceived self-control, vigour, and achievement motivation, further reinforcing the maladaptive nature of SPP (Childs & Stoeber, 2010; Klibert et al., 2005). Additionally, SPP is associated consistently with identity issues, negative self-views, and a failure to satisfy core psychological needs (Flett et al., 2022).

The developmental roots of perfectionism are unclear. On one hand, perfectionism is likely to develop gradually over time and is influenced by familial experiences, particularly interactions with parents (Walton et al., 2020). On the other hand, perfectionism likely stems from one's personality (Dunkley et al., 2012). Regardless of its roots, perfectionists frequently struggle with unconditional self-acceptance (Hewitt et al., 2017). They constantly seek approval and avoid disapproval from others by pursuing very high performance and quality standards (Flett et al., 2003). Thus, further investigation of the potentially associated factors is essential, as the present study aimed.

Adaptive and maladaptive forms of perfectionism exist in both positive and negative dimensions, with maladaptive perfectionism mainly reflecting in negative forms of perfectionism, such as doubting behaviour and fear of making mistakes, and adaptive perfectionism reflecting in positive forms of perfectionism (Kung & Chan, 2014). Positive perfectionism is negatively associated with emotional eating, and negative perfectionism is positively associated with emotional eating. However, existing research has primarily focused on the negative aspects of perfectionism, with positive aspects being often overlooked (Fang & Liu, 2022).

Therefore, adaptive perfectionism is associated with various positive psychological outcomes such as lower levels of perceived stress (Rice & Richardson, 2014), positive beliefs about one's personality attributes, and having a clear self-concept (Lo & Abbott, 2019). On the other hand, maladaptive perfectionism is associated with adverse psychological outcomes such as higher levels of perceived stress, self-criticism, suppression, and depression (Rice & Richardson, 2014), lower levels of self-compassion that leads to greater psychological distress (Koutra et al., 2023; Relojo, 2016), more negative-related beliefs about one's personality attributes and a less clear self-concept (Lo & Abbott, 2019).

Perfectionism and perceived parenting styles

Baumrind (1971) initially described a tripartite parenting model encompassing three parenting styles: authoritarian, authoritative, and permissive (Baumrind, 1971). The model was based on responsiveness and demandingness, which stemmed from the traditional parental dimensions of warmth and strictness (Schaefer, 1959; Sears et al., 1957). Later, four styles emerged, combining responsiveness and demandingness and adding neglectful styles. These styles are conceptualised along two dimensions: warmth/acceptance versus coldness/rejection and demandingness versus tolerance. A caregiver's parenting style can profoundly affect individuals by reinforcing behaviours and attitudes associated with the style or failing to meet the child's needs. For example, the need for acceptance might be met with a cold and rejecting attitude from a parent, potentially resulting in severe consequences for the individual's future psychological functioning (Baumrind, 1971).

The authoritarian style is characterised by high control, demandingness, and low warmth and involvement (Delvecchio et al., 2020). Authoritarian parents are directive and demanding of their children but generally unresponsive. They value obedience and status and expect their standards to be met in any circumstance, often resorting to punitive or forceful measures when they are not met (Baumrind, 2012). Unlike the exchange of opinions and disobedience, respect for authority, work, and preserving traditional order and structure are encouraged. Consequently, children raised by authoritarian parents tend to have lower self-efficacy (Baumrind et al., 2010), social competence (Baumrind, 1971), and more internalising and externalising problems (Braza et al., 2015). Authoritarian parenting can also cause aggressiveness in children, making them socially inept, shy, and unable to make their own decisions confidently (Ghosh, 2021).

The authoritative style is characterised by high acceptance and behavioural control, low psychological control, high responsiveness, and warmth to their children (Delvecchio et al., 2020). Authoritative parents are often seen as affectionate, encouraging, and controlling while supporting children's autonomy (Baumrind, 2013). Autonomy and compliance with discipline are encouraged. Firm control is exercised during disagreements without imposing unnecessary restrictions on the children. Thus, the core of authoritative parenting is to maintain a balance between imposing limits and promoting independence through guidance and support. Consequently, children with authoritative parents tend to be more cooperative, friendly, and emotionally stable (Garcia & Garcia, 2009). Authoritative parenting was considered the optimal and most beneficial parenting style, resulting in less maladaptive behaviour in children (Luyckx et al., 2011).

The permissive style is characterised by high responsiveness and low demandingness. Permissive parents are nonpunitive and affirmative of their children's impulses, allowing children to self-regulate and avoid confrontation while not holding themselves accountable for shaping the children's behaviour (Luyckx et al., 2011). Permissive parents prefer to be seen as friends instead of parents and do not attribute much importance to rules or structure, sometimes placing their own needs before their children's (Cox et al., 2018). Consequently, children with permissive parents tend to display lower self-esteem and have problems with developing appropriate forms of self-regulation (DeHart et al., 2006). Additionally, permissive parenting is positively associated with deviant peer affiliation and alcohol use, with permissive parenting leading to delinquent behaviour and substance use via deviant peer association (Hinnant et al., 2016).

Previous research highlighted a significant relationship between parenting styles and perfectionism. For instance, it was suggested that maladaptive perfectionism is positively linked to the authoritarian parenting style of both mothers and fathers and negatively related to the authoritative parenting style of both parents (Soysa & Weiss, 2014). Moreover, most perfectionists identify their family environment as the primary source of their perfectionism, with 30 out of 37 participants attributing it to their parents—females citing both parents and males primarily their fathers—while 12 participants pointed to themselves and 4 to their siblings (Slaney & Ashby, 1996). Furthermore, maternal control and negative affect are associated with SPP in children. In contrast, only maternal control is associated with SOP in children, suggesting that parental control and demandingness play an important role in the development of multidimensional perfectionism in children, which further transforms into depressive symptoms (Kenney-Benson & Pomerantz, 2005). Similarly, individuals who experienced parental psychological control tend to display higher levels of maladaptive perfectionism one year later, which in turn predicts increased levels of depressive symptoms one year later, further suggesting that parental demandingness plays an important role in the development of maladaptive perfectionism (Soenens et al., 2008). Additionally, perceived authoritarian parenting and parental harshness is associated with greater levels of concern over mistakes and doubts about actions, two measures of perfectionism that reflect maladaptive perfectionism through self-criticism and self-doubt (Kawamura et al., 2002).

Further supporting the influence of the family environment, Flett et al. (2002) suggested that perfectionism often develops in families where achievement and strict adherence to rules are highly valued. This result suggests a connection between perfectionism and parenting styles based on high levels of involvement and demandingness (e.g., authoritarian, authoritative), with several studies indicating a positive association between authoritarian parenting and maladaptive perfectionism (Craddock et al., 2009; Miller et al., 2012)

Investigating the relationship between parenting styles, gender, and multidimensional perfectionism, Hibbard and Walton (2014) found that some maladaptive aspects of perfectionism were diminished for individuals who grew up with authoritative parents. Specifically, male participants reported lower levels of self-doubt about their ability, while female participants reported lower levels of parental criticism. However, both male and female participants who grew up with an authoritarian parenting style reported higher parental expectations, criticism, and self-doubt, with female participants showing less concern about making mistakes than male participants. Moreover, the permissive parenting style was negatively associated with parental criticism in the case of all participants and concern over mistakes in the case of male participants. Parental criticism has been linked to SPP (Smith et al., 2022), and concern over mistakes has been linked to maladaptive perfectionism (Kawamura et al., 2002).

Moreover, maladaptive perfectionism is positively associated with authoritarian parenting and negatively associated with authoritative parenting for both mothers and fathers (Soysa & Weiss, 2014). Similarly, psychologically controlling parenting is linked to maladaptive perfectionism and goal avoidance in college students (Fletcher et al., 2012). Authoritarian parenting is associated with greater maladaptive perfectionism and lower creativity (Miller et al., 2012). Similarly, SOP and SPP are associated with authoritarian parenting styles but not permissive and authoritative parenting styles (Walton et al., 2020). In addition, the authoritarian parenting style is positively associated with maladaptive perfectionism, while the permissive and authoritative parenting styles are negatively associated with maladaptive perfectionism (Watabe, 2018). Furthermore, parenting styles and parental perfectionism influence children's perfectionism. Mothers' SOP predicts daughters' SOP and sons' SPP, and mothers' SPP is associated with daughters' SOP and SPP (Carmo et al., 2021). Additionally, both the permissive and authoritative parenting styles play an important role in developing child perfectionism. Overall, maternal parenting style is a stronger predictor of children's perfectionism development than paternal parenting style. Thus, both mothers' and fathers' authoritative parenting style negatively predicts SPP in girls, whereas the permissive parenting style positively predicts SPP in girls. However, the authoritative and permissive parenting styles did not predict SOP in girls and SPP or SOP in boys.

Perfectionism and perceived parenting styles

Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) represent a multilayered construct that encompasses a wide range of categories, such as physical, sexual, and emotional abuse, physical and emotional neglect, exposure to parental mental illness, divorce, substance abuse within the household, intimate partner violence, or the incarceration of a family member (Felitti et al., 1998). Boullier and Blair (2018) defined ACEs as potentially traumatic events that can have long-lasting adverse effects on health and general well-being. Such experiences include maltreatment, abuse, and living in an environment that is harmful to children's development (Boullier & Blair, 2018).

ACEs are considered to be significant precursors to cognitive and behavioural problems in adulthood, given the high prevalence of such experiences. For instance, a recent study showed that 57.8% of the 200,000 participants reported at least one ACE, while 21.5% reported three or more (Giano et al., 2020). Further, ACEs seem to contribute to exploring the roots of perfectionism. For instance, Chen et al. (2019) found a significant positive association between socially prescribed perfectionism and ACEs, specifically abuse. However, the study could not establish a link between ACEs and self-oriented or other-oriented perfectionism. Chen et al. (2019) investigated the relationship between ACEs, multidimensional perfectionism, and perfectionistic self-presentation. The results showed that only abuse was linked to SPP, whereas family dysfunction and neglect showed no significant correlation with perfectionism. Likewise, abuse (emotional, physical, and sexual) showed a positive correlation to all three facets of perfectionistic self-presentation: self-promotion, nondisclosure, and nondisclosure of imperfection (Chen et al., 2019).

Other studies also suggested that maladaptive perfectionism is significantly associated with childhood trauma, emotional dysregulation, and academic anxiety (Doboş et al., 2021). Early abuse and neglect are significant predictors of maladaptive perfectionism in young adults, which is also positively associated with higher stress levels (Grad et al., 2023).

Additionally, distinct conceptual frameworks of perfectionism, such as the PDSM and the Social Reaction Model of Perfectionism, claim that perfectionism develops as a mechanism of coping with harmful parenting practices and traumatic experiences (Flett et al., 2002; Hewitt et al., 2017). Thus, perfectionism develops to deal with feelings of despair, shame, and lack of control or security. Several studies reported significant associations between childhood trauma and perfectionism. For example, sexual abuse and the total number of ACEs are positively associated with perfectionism (Kong & Bernstein, 2009). Furthermore, a history of early childhood trauma is associated with self-criticism and perfectionism in patient populations suffering from chronic fatigue syndrome (Kempke et al., 2013).

The present study

This study advances the academic literature by discussing ACEs and perceived parenting styles as possible causes for SOP and SPP based on the widely recognised conceptual and theoretical framework of multidimensional perfectionism (Hewitt & Flett, 1991). Furthermore, we were

interested in exploring possible gender differences between ACEs, the permissive, authoritative, and authoritarian parenting styles, and SOP and SPP. In our attempt to predict SOP and SPP, we assumed that: (H1) Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) would significantly predict higher levels of socially prescribed perfectionism (SPP).

Adverse childhood experiences, such as abuse, neglect, and household dysfunction, have been consistently linked to distress and disruptions in self-worth development (Coates et al., 2013; Felitti et al., 1998). These experiences may motivate individuals to seek external validation and approval, which is central to SPP (Hewitt & Flett, 1991). Specifically, individuals who experience ACEs may develop SPP as a maladaptive coping mechanism to regain a sense of control and avoid further rejection or exclusion (Chen et al., 2019). Additionally, sexual abuse and the total number of ACEs have been previously linked to perfectionism (Kong & Bernstein, 2009). This hypothesis is further supported by research indicating that childhood trauma is positively associated with maladaptive perfectionism, specifically SPP, as individuals may internalise the harsh and demanding environments they experienced during childhood (Grad et al., 2023; Kong & Bernstein, 2009).

Next, we assumed that (H2) The perceived permissive parenting style would significantly predict lower levels of socially prescribed perfectionism (SPP). Permissive parenting, characterised by low demandingness and high responsiveness, is associated with a lack of structure and discipline (Baumrind, 1971; Luyckx et al., 2011). This parenting style may reduce the likelihood of individuals perceiving external pressures or unrealistic standards, which are central to SPP (Hewitt & Flett, 1991). Previous research showed that permissive parenting is negatively associated with maladaptive perfectionism, as it does not foster the high external expectations characteristic of SPP (Watabe, 2018). Additionally, permissive parenting is negatively associated with concern over mistakes and parental criticism, two measures associated with maladaptive perfectionism (Hibbard & Walton, 2014). Therefore, it is hypothesised that permissive parenting will predict lower levels of SPP.

We further assumed that (H3) The perceived authoritative parenting style would significantly predict lower socially prescribed perfectionism (SPP) levels. Authoritative parenting, which combines high responsiveness with appropriate levels of demandingness, is associated with positive psychological outcomes, including higher self-esteem and emotional stability (Baumrind, 2013; Garcia & Garcia, 2009). This parenting style fosters an environment where children feel supported and valued, reducing the need for external validation through perfectionistic behaviours (Soysa & Weiss, 2014). Additionally, the authoritative parenting style is negatively associated with parental criticism and concern over mistakes, both associated with maladaptive perfectionism (Watabe, 2018). Thus, it is hypothesised that authoritative parenting will predict lower levels of SPP.

Next, we assumed that (H4) The perceived authoritarian parenting style will significantly predict higher self-oriented perfectionism (SOP) levels. Authoritarian parenting, characterised by high demandingness and low warmth, often involves strict rules and high expectations without emotional support (Baumrind, 1971; Delvecchio et al., 2020). Children raised in such environments may internalise parents' high standards, leading to the development of SOP, where they impose unrealistic expectations on themselves (Hewitt & Flett, 1991). Research has consistently shown that authoritarian parenting is positively associated with maladaptive perfectionism, as children may resort to perfectionistic behaviours to meet parental expectations and avoid criticism (Miller et al., 2012; Walton et al., 2020). Therefore, it is hypothesised that authoritarian parenting will predict higher levels of SOP.

(H5) The perceived authoritarian parenting style will significantly predict higher socially prescribed perfectionism (SPP) levels. Authoritarian parenting, emphasising obedience and high external standards, may lead children to perceive that others, not just their parents, impose demanding expectations on them (Baumrind, 1971). This externalisation of high standards is a core feature of SPP (Hewitt & Flett, 1991). Empirical studies have consistently shown that authoritarian parenting is positively associated with maladaptive perfectionism, specifically SPP, as children may generalise the harsh and demanding environment of their upbringing to their broader social context (Soysa & Weiss, 2014; Walton et al., 2020). Thus, it is hypothesised that authoritarian parenting will predict higher levels of SPP.

METHOD

Participants

Our sample consisted of 156 participants, of whom 88 were female (56.4%) and 68 were male (43.6%). The participants' ages ranged from 18 to 51 ($M = 23.6$, $SD = 4.56$). Most participants ($N = 136$, 87.1%) were residents of urban areas. The participants were students from various universities around the country enrolled in bachelor's and master's programs in different academic years (from 1 to 5). Participation was voluntary.

Measures

The Multidimensional Perfectionism Scale (MPS), developed by Hewitt and Flett (1991), measured SOP and SPP. The MPS is one of the most widely used instruments in perfectionism research and has been validated across diverse populations, including students, clinical samples, and community samples (Hewitt & Flett, 1991). Only 30 items were selected, corresponding to the two dimensions of perfectionism investigated in this research. Participants answered on a seven-point Likert-type scale (1=not at all, 7=very characteristic for me), rating the extent to which the situation described in the items occurred to them. The items selected for SOP focused on self-directed perfectionist motivation and setting unrealistic standards for oneself (e.g., "I strive to be as perfect as I can be"). The items selected for SPP focused on the belief that others set an unrealistic performance standard for the individual in question (e.g., "I feel that people are too demanding of me"). The maximum score that can be obtained for both perfectionism dimensions was 105 (Cronbach-Alpha for the SOP scale = .907; For the SPP scale = .851). The scale's ability to distinguish between different dimensions of perfectionism—such as SOP, SPP, and other-oriented perfectionism—aligns with the study's focus on understanding the distinct developmental pathways of SOP and SPP. By using the MPS, this study ensures that the measurement of perfectionism is consistent with the theoretical framework proposed by Hewitt and Flett (1991), which posits that perfectionism is a multidimensional construct with both adaptive and maladaptive manifestations.

The Adverse Childhood Experiences Questionnaire (ACE-Q), developed by Felitti et al. (1998), was chosen to assess adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) due to its ability to assess numerous categories of traumatic events that are known to have long-term psychological and behavioural consequences. This ability to measure various experiences is critical for capturing the multifaceted nature of childhood trauma, which has been linked to the development of maladaptive perfectionism in prior research (Chen et al., 2019; Grad et al., 2023). Participants answered 10 "yes or no" questions, indicating whether they experienced the phenomenon described before turning 18. The items of this scale focused on physical abuse (e.g., "Did a parent or adult in the household often... Push, grab, slap, or throw something at you? Or... Ever hit you so hard that you had marks or were injured?"), sexual abuse, emotional abuse, physical neglect, emotional neglect, mental illness, divorce, substance abuse, violence against the mother, and incarceration of a family member. The maximum score for this instrument was 10, and a higher score indicated a higher occurrence of adverse childhood experiences (Cronbach alpha = .707).

The Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ), developed by Buri (1991), measured permissive, authoritative, and authoritarian parenting styles, due to its strong theoretical grounding in Baumrind's (1971) parenting typology and its widespread use in psychological research. The Parental Authority Questionnaire assesses parenting styles through two dimensions: demandingness (control) and responsiveness (warmth), which are central to understanding how parenting practices influence child development (Baumrind, 1971; Delvecchio et al., 2020). Participants answered on a 5-point Likert-type scale (1 = never, 5 = always), rating the extent to which the situation described in the items occurred to them (Permissive, e.g., "My parents do not view themselves as responsible for directing and guiding my behaviour"; Authoritarian, e.g., "My parents feel that wise parents should teach their children early just who is boss in the family"; Authoritative e.g., "My parents consistently give us direction and guidance rationally and objectively"). Participants were asked to refer to the parent or caretaker who had the strongest influence on them or whom they felt the closest to. Each parenting style was measured with 10 items, and the maximum score that can be obtained for any parenting style was 50 (Cronbach-Alpha for the overall scale = .714).

The study's objectives to explore the link between adverse childhood experiences, perceived parenting styles, and multidimensional perfectionism guided the selection of these measures. The MPS, ACE-Q, and PAQ were chosen not only for their strong psychometric properties but also for their ability to capture the interplay between early life experiences, parenting practices, and the development of perfectionistic traits.

Procedure

The research link was open for a month, in November 2023, to any potential participant (aged 18 or older). Facebook, Instagram, and other social media platforms (such as student groups) were used to spread the invitation to complete the questionnaire. The participants were informed about the participation requirements and their right to withdraw from the study at all times. After providing informed consent, participants completed a demographic questionnaire mentioning their age and area of residence, followed by the ACEs, parenting styles, and perfectionism scales. The research protocol was developed following the ethical guidelines from the university where the authors are affiliated and the 2013 Helsinki Declaration.

Data analysis

Data cleaning measures were taken before proceeding with the analyses. No participants were excluded from the sample. Next, we computed the Skewness and Kurtosis values for our variables (i.e., ACEs, the two dimensions of perfectionism, and the three parenting styles) to assess the normality of the distribution. All the Skewness values were within the $2/-2$ limit, and the Kurtosis values were within $7/-7$ limit, indicating normality (see Table 1), as suggested by Byrne (2013) and Hair et al. (2010). Statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS program, version 26 (George & Mallery, 2019).

RESULTS

Table 1
 Descriptive statistics for the study's main variables ($N = 156$)

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
ACE	2.22	2.09	0	8	0.86	-0.02
SOP	72.24	16.24	34	105	-0.13	-0.61
SPP	55.81	14.43	17	89	-0.04	-0.42
Permissive	27.28	8.04	10	46	0.02	-0.52
Authoritarian	27.12	9.87	10	50	0.28	-0.64
Authoritative	31.78	9.46	10	50	-0.37	-0.33

Note: ACE = adverse childhood experiences; SOP = self-oriented perfectionism; SPP = socially prescribed perfectionism; Permissive = permissive parenting style; Authoritarian = authoritarian parenting style; Authoritative = authoritative parenting style

Table 2
 Zero-order correlations between the main variables ($N = 156$)

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
ACE	1					
SOP	0.1	1				
SPP	0.25**	0.45**	1			
Permissive	-0.3**	-0.24**	-0.25**	1		
Authoritarian	0.38**	0.36**	0.39**	-0.55**	1	
Authoritative	-0.39**	-0.05	-0.26**	0.64**	-0.49	1

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .001$

We first computed zero-order correlations to investigate the associations between the variables and test for potential multicollinearity (see Table 2). The data suggested that SOP and SPP were positively associated. Also, there was a positive association between ACEs and SPP ($r = .25, p = .002$) and a positive but non-significant association between ACEs and SOP ($r = .101, p = .209$). The permissive parenting style was negatively correlated with SOP ($r = -.24, p = .002$) and SPP ($r = -.25, p = .001$). The authoritative parenting style was negatively associated with SPP ($r = -.26, p = .001$) and negatively but non-significantly associated with SOP ($r = -.05, p = .52$). Finally, the authoritarian parenting style was positively associated with SOP ($r = .36, p < .001$) and SPP ($r = .39, p < .001$).

Next, we investigated possible gender differences among our primary variables. T-test results suggested significant differences between male and female participants concerning ACEs and the authoritative parenting style. In the case of ACEs, $t(154) = -3.19, p < .001$, with female participants ($M = 2.68$) scoring higher than male participants ($M = 1.63$). Significant differences were also found in terms of the authoritative parenting style, $t(154) = 2.81, p = .006$, with male participants ($M = 34.16$) scoring higher than female participants ($M = 29.95$). No significant differences were found for the permissive and authoritarian parenting styles or SOP and SPP.

Based on these findings, we performed a simple and multiple hierarchical regression, one for each type of perfectionism, using ACEs and the three parenting styles as predictors. As shown in Table 3, the simple regression model for SOP was significant $F(1;154) = 23.85, p < .001$. The authoritarian parenting styles explained 12.9% of the variance in SOP. Therefore, the authoritarian parenting style was a significant predictor ($\beta = .36, p < .001$).

Table 3
 Simple regression model for participants' self-oriented perfectionism ($N = 156$)

Variable	B	SE	β
Authoritarian	0.6	0.12	0.366**

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .001$

Also, as shown in Table 4, the hierarchical multiple regression for SPP was significant $F(4,151) = 7.66, p < .001$. ACEs and the permissive, authoritarian, and authoritative parenting styles explained 16.9% of the variance in SPP. One significant predictor was authoritarian parenting style ($\beta = .32, p = .001$). ACE ($\beta = .10, p = .21$), along with the permissive ($\beta = -.01, p = .92$) and authoritative ($\beta = -.05, p = .58$) parenting styles, were not significant predictors for SPP.

Table 4
 Hierarchical regression model for participants' socially prescribed perfectionism ($N = 156$)

Variable	B	95% CI for B		SE B	β	R^2	ΔR^2
		LL	UL				
Step 1						.063	.063*
ACE	1.73	.66	2.79	.53	.25**		
Step 2						.099	.036***
ACE	1.31	.22	2.41	.55	.19*		
Permissive	-.35	-.64	-.07	.14	-.19*		
Step 3						.167	.068***
ACE	.78	-.32	1.88	.55	.11		
Permissive	-.07	-.39	.24	.16	-.04		
Authoritarian	.47	.21	.74	.13	.32**		
Step 4						.169	.002***
ACE	.70	-.42	1.84	.57	.10		
Permissive	-.01	-.38	.35	.18	-.01		
Authoritarian	.46	.19	.74	.13	.32**		
Authoritative	-.08	-.39	.22	.15	-.05		

Note. CI = confidence interval; LL = lower limit; UL = upper limit; ACE = adverse childhood experiences; Permissive = permissive parenting style; Authoritarian = authoritarian parenting style; Authoritative = authoritative parenting style; * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$

DISCUSSION

This study explored the link between multidimensional perfectionism, ACEs, and parenting styles. Previous studies suggested that ACEs and authoritarian, authoritative, and permissive parenting styles predict SPP (Chen et al., 2019; Soysa & Weiss, 2014; Walton et al., 2018; Watabe, 2018), while other studies suggested that only authoritarian parenting style predicts SOP (Walton et al., 2020).

The study found that the authoritarian parenting style was a significant predictor of both SOP ($\beta = .36, p < .001$) and SPP ($\beta = .32, p = .001$). This aligns with previous research indicating that authoritarian parenting, characterised by high demandingness and low warmth, is associated with maladaptive perfectionism (Walton et al., 2020; Soysa & Weiss, 2014).

These findings support Baumrind's (1971) theoretical framework, which suggests that authoritarian parenting fosters an environment of high external control and low emotional support. In such environments, children may internalise the high standards imposed by their parents, leading to the development of SOP (Hewitt & Flett, 1991). Additionally, externalising these standards may contribute to the development of SPP, as individuals may perceive that others (not just their parents), impose similarly demanding expectations (Hewitt et al., 2017). This supports the multidimensional model of perfectionism, which suggests that perfectionistic behaviours often emerge as coping mechanisms in response to unmet psychological needs, such as safety and connection (Hewitt et al., 2017). Additionally, this supports previous research showing that mothers' use of control plays an important role in predicting SOP and SPP (Kenney-Benson & Pomerantz, 2005). This result is consistent with past research showing that individuals who grew up with authoritarian caretakers tend to be more anxious and overwhelmed by challenges than other children (Hart et al., 2003). A

potential explanation might reside in parental warmth's role in alleviating the adverse effects of parental demandingness. Therefore, high demandingness, without being accompanied by high warmth, results in maladaptive aspects of perfectionism and SPP. However, our results indicate that the authoritarian parenting style predicted SOP, highlighting the importance of parental demandingness. Authoritarian parents demonstrate a pronounced need to control and evaluate their children's behaviour and attitudes, leaving little room for children to choose their path or establish their standards. Instead, standards imposed by authoritarian parents are often exaggerated and reinforced by emphasising obedience and respect for authority (Baumrind, 1971). In response to such rigid parental attitudes, some children might adopt a different strategy, such as internalising parental attitudes and expectations. Therefore, individuals who score high on SOP might integrate such standards and adopt them as their own so that if their parents set very high standards for them, they will set very high standards for themselves. Therefore, the self-oriented perfectionists' intrinsic motivation might stem from the internalised standards of the individuals' parents. This explanation highlights the importance of the demandingness dimension of parenting styles, which plays a role in the upbringing of perfectionistic individuals. Additionally, this result supports several other studies that reported a link between authoritarian parenting, parental harshness, and maladaptive or multidimensional perfectionism (Kawamura et al., 2002; Kenney-Benson & Pomerantz, 2005; Soenens et al., 2008).

Another primary goal of this study was to prove that ACEs predict SPP. While ACEs were positively correlated with SPP ($r = .25, p = .002$), they did not emerge as a significant predictor in the regression model ($\beta = .10, p = .21$). This does not align with previous research suggesting that ACEs are significant predictors of maladaptive perfectionism (Grad et al., 2023). This result also contradicts Chen et al. (2019), who state that perfectionistic behaviours (e.g., SPP style) are usually acquired as a means of regaining personal control that was lost after a traumatic event (e.g., abuse). Furthermore, this result also contradicts Kong & Bernstein (2009), who found that sexual abuse and the total number of ACEs are positively associated with perfectionism. The lack of a significant predictive relationship between ACEs and SPP may indicate that other factors mediate the impact of childhood trauma on perfectionism.

The permissive parenting style was negatively correlated with SPP ($r = -.25, p = .001$), but it did not emerge as a significant predictor in the regression models. Similarly, the authoritative parenting style was negatively correlated with SPP ($r = -.26, p = .001$) but was not a significant predictor. These results do not align with previous research on permissive parenting, authoritative parenting, and SPP or maladaptive perfectionism (Flett et al., 2002; Hibbard & Walton, 2014; Soysa & Weiss, 2014; Watabe, 2018). Thus, our results suggest that these parenting styles may play a less direct role in developing perfectionism than authoritarian parenting. In the case of the permissive parenting style, one possible explanation might stem from the fact that demandingness may play an important role in predicting perfectionism.

In contrast, warmth may not contribute to the development of perfectionism. Therefore, in the absence of parental demandingness and its associations with parental criticism and concern over mistakes, parental warmth may not play an important role in developing SPP. However, the authoritative parenting style involves both parental demandingness and warmth. Thus, although parental warmth may not play an important role in predicting perfectionism, it may have a buffering effect on parental demandingness. Therefore, parental warmth may play an important role in mitigating the adverse effects of parental demandingness that are responsible for developing socially prescribed perfectionism. This finding challenges the assumption that parenting styles influence all maladaptive perfectionism equally and calls for a more refined theoretical framework that considers the interplay between parenting dimensions (e.g., warmth, demandingness).

Theoretical and practical implications. The findings of our study have several important theoretical implications. Firstly, this study contributes to the literature on multidimensional perfectionism and the upbringing factors that might have impacted it. Second, by examining the roles of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) and perceived parenting styles in the development of self-oriented perfectionism (SOP) and socially prescribed perfectionism (SPP), this study provides empirical support for the theoretical frameworks proposed by Hewitt and Flett (1991) and Baumrind (1971). Specifically, the results suggest that parental demandingness, unlike parental warmth, plays a central role in shaping perfectionistic personality traits, further suggesting that authoritarian parenting – characterised by high demandingness and low warmth – is a significant predictor of both SOP and SPP (Walton et al., 2020; Soysa & Weiss, 2014).

Furthermore, the study also extends the theoretical understanding of how ACEs influence perfectionism. While the findings did not support ACEs as a significant predictor of SPP, the positive correlation between ACEs and SPP suggests that traumatic childhood experiences may still play a role in the development of maladaptive perfectionism, particularly in individuals who perceive their social environment as demanding and critical (Chen et al., 2019; Grad et al., 2023).

From a practical standpoint, the findings of this study might have several implications for parents, educators, or even mental health professionals. The strong association between authoritarian parenting and both self-oriented perfectionism (SOP) and socially prescribed perfectionism (SPP) emphasises the need for interventions that address maladaptive parenting practices. Parenting programs that emphasise the importance of warmth and demandingness could help diminish the development of perfectionistic tendencies in children and adolescents. For mental health professionals, our findings highlight the importance of assessing childhood experiences and parenting styles when working with clients who exhibit perfectionistic personality traits. Additionally, therapeutic interventions and strategies could be tailored to address the specific needs of individuals with high levels of SOP or SPP, particularly those who have experienced an authoritarian parenting style in their upbringing.

The present study might also serve as a starting point for future research exploring these links and possible frameworks to better understand the genesis of multidimensional perfectionism. This research added to the scarce literature regarding the causes of multidimensional perfectionism among Romanian individuals. It also highlighted that only the authoritarian parenting style might be considered when discussing the role of parenting styles in the roots of SOP and SPP, emphasising the importance of parental demandingness in the absence of parental warmth.

Limitations and future directions

While this study provides valuable insights, it is not without its limitations, such as the relatively small number of participants added to the cross-sectional nature of the survey, which lowers our findings' generalisability. First, the sample was, for the most part, comprised of young, educated individuals from urban areas. While this sample is appropriate for examining perfectionism in emerging adulthood, it may not fully capture the experiences of individuals in other life stages or contexts.

Second, university students are often similar in terms of socioeconomic status and cognitive abilities, which may limit the diversity of the sample. This similarity could affect the external validity of the findings, as the relationships between adverse childhood experiences, parenting styles, and perfectionism may vary across different demographic groups. For example, individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds or those with less access to educational resources may experience different patterns of parenting or childhood adversity, which could influence the development of perfectionism in ways not captured by this study.

Additionally, the student sample may be subject to selection bias. Individuals who participate in psychological research may differ from the general population regarding personality traits, motivation, educational background, and personal interests. For example, students who display higher levels of perfectionism or are more academically oriented may be more likely to participate in studies, potentially affecting the results. This bias may hinder the applicability of the findings to individuals who do not have academic interests or do not have higher levels of perfectionism. Furthermore, the participants' answer desirability might have been affected by the self-reporting measures of the survey. Moreover, this study did not assess both paternal and maternal parenting styles, and the participants were instructed to refer to the parenting style of the parent or caretaker who had the strongest influence on them or whom they felt the closest to, as a means of avoiding data biases for participants who did not grow up with both parents.

Future research might address these concerns by including more diverse samples. Longitudinal studies could also provide deeper insights into how perfectionism develops over time and across different life stages. Additionally, experimental approaches could help mitigate the potential biases associated with self-report measures and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to multidimensional perfectionism.

Finally, future research might add other significant variables, such as assessing of differences in parental perfectionism, intrinsic/extrinsic motivation, and harshness. Additionally, future research should focus on parental demandingness as a primary predictor of multidimensional perfectionism; an assessment of parental demandingness through multiple instruments and theoretical frameworks is required to capture the complex interplay of demandingness and multidimensional perfectionism. Furthermore, several constructs such as self-criticism and self-compassion could be investigated as mediators of the relationship between parenting styles, adverse childhood experiences, and perfectionism, as higher self-criticism and lower self-compassion are associated with maladaptive perfectionism and greater levels of psychological distress (Koutra et al., 2023; Rice & Richardson, 2014). Moreover, future research should address whether there are differences in how paternal or maternal control and demandingness predict self-oriented and socially prescribed perfectionism.

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